

Complete vs Restricted Active Space Perturbation Theory Calculation of the Cr₂ Potential Energy Surface

Fernando Ruipérez^a, Francesco Aquilante^b, Jesus M. Ugalde^a
and Ivan Infante^{*a}

^aKimika Fakultatea, Euskal Herriko Unibertsitatea, and
Donostia International Physics Center (DIPC),
P. K. 1072, 20080 Donostia, Euskadi (Spain).

^bDepartment of Physical Chemistry, University of Geneva
Chemical Center, 30 Quai Ernest-Ansermet,
CH-1211, Geneva (Switzerland).

*Corresponding Author: iinfant76@gmail.com; fax:+34-943-015270

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Abstract

In this paper we calculate the potential energy surface (PES) and the spectroscopic constants of the chromium dimer using the recently developed second-order perturbation theory restricted active space (RASPT2) method. This approach is benchmarked against available experimental measurements and the complete active space second-order perturbation theory (CASPT2), which is nowadays established as one of the most accurate theoretical models available. Dissociation energies, vibrational frequencies and bond distances are computed at the RASPT2 level using several reference spaces. The major advantage of the RASPT2 method is that with a limited number of configuration state functions, it can reproduce well the equilibrium bond length and the vibrational frequency of the Cr dimer. On the other hand, the PES is well described only at short distances, while at large distances it compares very poorly with the CASPT2. The dissociation energy is also ill-behaved, but its value can be largely improved using a simple workaround that we explain in the text. In the paper we also

address the effect of the Ionization Potential Electron Affinity (IPEA) shift (a parameter introduced in the zeroth-order Hamiltonian in the CASPT2 method to include the effect of two-electron terms) and show how its default value of 0.25 is not suitable for a proper description of the PES and of the spectroscopic parameters and must be changed to a more sound value of 0.45.

1 Introduction

The interest in small transition metal (TM) clusters has grown rapidly in recent years because of their wide range of applications in different fields, such as catalysis, optics, biomedicine, environment, etc.¹⁻⁵ TM clusters also serve as a bridge between bulk materials and nanomaterials, since they are experimentally accessible and, at the same time, still tractable with very accurate theoretical models.

From a theoretical standpoint, the description of transition metal elements and their compounds is particularly challenging due to the presence of a dense manifold of low-lying states generated by the partial occupation of the nd and $(n + 1)s$ shells. These factors can lead to ground state (or excited state) wavefunctions of multireference character, where a large number of configurations is needed to properly account for *static* correlation effects, of fundamental importance for the accurate description of potential energy surfaces and dissociation energies. This precludes in many cases the use of post-Hartree-Fock methods, and poses great challenges to density functional theory (DFT), as these approaches work best for the accurate description of the *dynamic* correlation. Under these circumstances, a multiconfigurational model like the complete active space self-consistent field method followed by second-order perturbation theory, CASSCF/CASPT2,⁶⁻¹⁰ is particularly attractive to achieve a proper description of both types of correlation energy.

The recent development of the so-called *ab initio* density fitting and Cholesky-based algorithms¹¹⁻¹⁴ has expanded considerably the range of molecular sizes for which CASSCF/CASPT2 calculations are feasible. A number of insightful studies of diverse chemical problems¹⁵⁻¹⁸ has been possible as a result of these improvements in theory and algorithms. Unfortunately, the application of CASSCF/CASPT2 is still limited by the solution of the configuration interaction (CI) problem, a step where the computational cost increases factorially with the size of the active space. This adverse circumstance prevents its use for the study of TM clusters with more than two atoms. In order to overcome such limitation, new theoretical models have been introduced to reduce drastically the number of configuration state

functions (CSFs) in the CI step. In particular, the restricted active space self-consistent field method, followed by second-order perturbation theory, RASSCF/RASPT2,^{19–22} is emerging as a promising alternative. Although RASSCF method was developed twenty years ago,^{19,20} its extension to include dynamical correlation, the so-called RASPT2 method,^{21,22} was successfully established only recently. Few applications can be found already in the literature with encouraging results.^{21,23–25}

To achieve the goal of studying TM clusters of increasing size, we decided to assess the performance of RASSCF/RASPT2 on a small albeit complex transition metal molecule: the chromium dimer.

The Cr₂ molecule poses a big challenge from a theoretical point of view because its ground state presents one of the most complicated electronic structures that can be found among metal dimers. The $^1\Sigma_g^+$ electronic ground state is highly multiconfigurational and the dominant CSF, $4s_g^2 3d\sigma_g^2 3d\pi_u^4 3d\delta_g^4$, weighs only 47%. Besides, the experimental potential energy surface (PES) shows, in addition to the relatively deep minimum at approximately 1.68 Å corresponding to the $3d - 3d$ interaction, a rather flat, shelf-like region, at about 2.5 Å, where the interaction between the diffuse $4s$ orbitals is dominant.²⁶ As a further complication, the dimer dissociates into two chromium atoms whose ground state has a high-spin open-shell electronic configuration 7S , with six unpaired electrons distributed as $3d^5 4s^1$. This means that the static electron correlation becomes dramatically important along the potential energy surface.

Popular exchange-correlation (xc) functionals within the framework of DFT have been demonstrated to describe poorly the PES and some of the spectroscopic constants. Only the BLYP functional is capable to reproduce the first minimum and the shelf-like potential along the PES, while traditional hybrid functionals like B3LYP and B3PB86 fail to show the region at 2.5 Å.²⁷ For all xc-functionals used, the stretching vibrational frequency is computed at about 800 cm⁻¹, almost two times larger than the experiment, 481 cm⁻¹. Furthermore, spin contamination affects all DFT results, pinpointing the fact that a single closed-shell configuration represents a too simplistic description of the bonding pattern in the Cr dimer.

A variety of post-HF calculations have been employed to study the Cr₂ PES,^{28,29} however for the purpose of this paper we focus on the ones based on the CASSCF/CASPT2 method. The first of these calculations showed severe problems with intruder states and the calculations were not able to reproduce the double minimum in the potential energy surface.³⁰ Years later, several improvements were included in the computational model, regarding basis sets, active space and zeroth-order Hamiltonian. The first attempt to solve the problem of the intruder states was the use of a modified zeroth-

order Hamiltonian, called as $g1$, and significant improvement was achieved. A deep inspection of the CASPT2 wavefunction revealed that the $4p$ orbitals were playing a major role in removing the intruder states, hence the original active space, which included 12 electrons in 12 orbitals (the $3d$ and $4s$ orbitals of the two atoms), called CAS(12/12), was extended to include four extra orbitals of $4p$ character, more precisely the 3 bonding combination $4p_\sigma$ and $4p_\pi$ and the antibonding $4p_\sigma^*$. Using this big active space it was possible to reproduce satisfactorily the shape of the potential energy surface, and the intruder-state problem was corrected applying a level shift of 0.3 au.³¹

In this work we show that it is possible to represent correctly the spectroscopic constants and the shape of the potential energy surface for Cr_2 using the original (12/12) active space that includes the $3d$ and $4s$ orbitals, provided that an optimal value of the IPEA shift (vide infra) is chosen. Moreover, with this value of the IPEA shift, we have investigated the possibility to use the less computational intensive RASSCF/RASPT2 method to determine the electronic structure and PES of Cr_2 . Our results also provide insights on how to use the method, and what its limitations are if applied to the study of bigger systems such as small metal clusters.

2 Details of the calculations

All-electron spin-free relativistic calculations were carried out using the Douglas-Kroll-Hess Hamiltonian.^{32,33} In the first step, complete active space self-consistent field calculations (CASSCF)⁶⁻⁸ are performed choosing an active space in which 12 electrons are distributed in the following 12 molecular orbitals, $4s\sigma_g$, $3d\sigma_g$, $3d\pi_u$, $3d\delta_g$, $4s\sigma_u^*$, $3d\sigma_u^*$, $3d\pi_g^*$ and $3d\delta_u^*$, composed of the $3d$ and $4s$ atomic orbitals of each Cr atom. Using this wavefunction, dynamical correlation effects are included through complete active space second-order perturbation theory calculations (CASPT2)^{9,10} using the ionization potential electron affinity (IPEA)-corrected zeroth-order Hamiltonian³⁴ and the so-called $g1$ modified zeroth-order Hamiltonian.³⁵ The use of an imaginary shift³⁶ of 0.2 au was necessary in order to avoid the presence of intruder states in the CASPT2 step, where the $3s$ and $3p$ closed shells are also correlated dynamically. In the (IPEA)-corrected calculations, different values of the IPEA shift, ϵ , were tested. Moreover, we have also performed calculations at the RASSCF/RASPT2¹⁹⁻²² level of theory, in which the zeroth-order wavefunction is obtained in a restricted active space (RAS). In the RASSCF method the active space is divided into three subspaces: RAS1, RAS2 and RAS3. RAS2 is identical to the CAS, where all possible spin- and symmetry-adapted configuration state functions are constructed, i.e. a full CI within

the selected space, while RAS1 and RAS3 are subspaces originally containing doubly occupied and empty orbitals, respectively. These two subspaces allow the generation of additional configuration state functions with the restriction that a maximum number of excitations may occur from RAS1 (to RAS2 and RAS3) and a maximum number of excitations may occur into RAS3 (from RAS1 and RAS2). This model can handle larger active spaces than regular CAS, provided that the resulting number of CSFs does not exceed the present limits. All calculations were performed with MOLCAS 7.4 code³⁷ and using a C_{2h} symmetry. We used the basis set developed by Roos³¹ for this system, which is obtained from the primitive basis set $21s15p10d6f4g$ of Pou *et al.*³⁸ contracted to $10s10p8d6f4g$.

The potential energy surface of the Cr dimer is scanned using the VIBROT program.³⁷ This program fits the potential to an analytical form using cubic splines and solves the ro-vibrational Schrödinger equation numerically. The energies are then analyzed in terms of spectroscopic constants, namely equilibrium bond length (R_e), dissociation energy (D_e and D_0) and fundamental vibrational frequency ($\Delta G_{1/2}$). The dissociation energy of the molecule can be also calculated by subtracting the ground state energy of the dimer at the equilibrium to the energy of the isolated atoms in their ground state calculated at the full CASPT2 level: $D'_e = 2 \times E[Cr(^7S)] - E[Cr_2(^1\Sigma_g^+)]$. Although this dissociation energy should be the same as the one computed with VIBROT, CASPT2 calculations lead to subtle differences due to possible numerical inconsistencies. For sake of clarity, we show both types of dissociation throughout the paper.

The effect of counterpoise correction is minimal: 0.002 Å on the bond distance, 0.03 eV on the dissociation energy and 10 cm^{-1} on the vibrational frequency. For this reason we consider the BSSE non influential for the overall discussion and we decided to avoid its computation for all the PES presented in this article.

3 Results

3.1 Effect of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian and IPEA shift

In the original formulation of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian in the CASPT2 method, a systematic error is introduced by defining a generalized effective one-electron Fock operator that does not include explicitly two-electron terms in the Hamiltonian. In this simplified framework, a non-balanced description of bond energies and electronic excitation energies can occur once the states

that are compared have different spin-multiplicity, in particular when one of the states is a closed-shell.³⁹

In order to correct this systematic error, Ghigo *et al.*³⁴ proposed a modification of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian by introducing a shift operator, the so-called Ionization Energy (IP) - Electron Affinity (EA) shift, or more simply IPEA shift ϵ , which modifies the diagonal elements of the generalized one-electron Fock matrix. Basically, in partially filled orbitals like the active orbitals in the CASSCF method, the shift modifies the diagonal elements of the Fock matrix in such a way that the energies of the active orbitals become closer to -IP, when an electron is excited out of these orbitals, and closer to -EA, when one electron is excited into one of them. This shift can be determined either using experimental results or by comparison with highly accurate calculations. For transition metals the value of ϵ varies between 0.2 and 0.4 au, with an average value of 0.25 au, which is currently the default value used in the present implementation of the zeroth-order Hamiltonian in MOLCAS.³⁷ The addition of this parameter considerably reduces the previously mentioned systematic errors found in CASPT2 calculations, however few studies carried out in some test cases have revealed that this is not the most appropriate value in every case.⁴⁰⁻⁴²

In this work we study how the variation of this parameter, ϵ , not only drastically affects the potential energy surface, but also the equilibrium bond length, the dissociation energy and the vibrational frequency of the Cr dimer. A summary of the results are shown in Table 1 and in Figure 1.

The theoretical potential energy surface calculated using the original $g1$ zeroth-order Hamiltonian is shown in Figure 1, together with the experimental curve. It is interesting to include the $g1$ result as it is the one based on previous calculations by Roos³¹ where a bigger active space was needed together with a level shift of 0.3 au in order to accurately describe the experimental PES. In our work, for consistency with the IPEA curves, we employed an active space that includes only $3d$ and $4s$ orbitals and an imaginary level shift of 0.2 au. Under these conditions, this Hamiltonian generates a curve that agrees reasonably well with the experiment regarding the overall shape, as it reproduces the shelf-like region (see green line in Figure 1). However the first minimum, located in the $3d - 3d$ region is much deeper than it should be and is about 0.6 eV more binding than the experimental value. Clearly, this approach is flawed since also the $\Delta G_{1/2}$ is overestimated by about 100 cm^{-1} as compared to the experiment. See Table 1 for more details.

When the IPEA Hamiltonian is employed, some very interesting results are obtained. Starting with $\epsilon = 0.25$, which is the default value, we notice that the shape of the curve around the $3d$ minimum is rather shallow, while the behavior of the curve is preserved in the $4s$ region (see red line in Figure

Figure 1: Potential energy surfaces obtained with different values of IPEA shift, ϵ and using the modified $g1$ Hamiltonian, together with the experimental curve. Bond distances in \AA and energies in kcal/mol. The asymptotic zero energy taken as reference is the total energy of the Cr atoms at a distance of 10 \AA .

Table 1: Spectroscopic constants obtained with the (IPEA)-corrected zeroth-order Hamiltonian for different values of IPEA shift (ϵ) and with the modified $g1$ zeroth-order Hamiltonian. The dissociation energies are calculated from the potential energy surfaces (D_e) and from two times the energy of the isolated atoms (D'_e). The vertical ionization potential and the experimental data are also shown. Distances in Å, vibrational frequencies in cm^{-1} and energies in eV.

ϵ	R_e	D_e	D'_e	D_0	$\Delta G_{1/2}$	IP
0.00	–	–	0.608	–	–	–
0.25	1.736	1.15	1.38	1.14	70	7.13
0.40	1.696	1.45	1.42		468	7.12
0.45	1.687	1.52	–	1.50	516	7.12
0.50	1.681	1.60	1.98	1.56	542	–
0.75	–	–	2.41	–	–	–
1.00	–	–	2.73	–	–	–
$g1^a$	1.682	2.12	2.13	2.09	551	7.08
$g1^b$	1.662	–	–	1.65	413	–
exp.	1.679 ^c	1.56	–	1.53 ^d	452 ^c	6.9988 ^d

^aThis work, ^b from Ref.,³¹ ^c from Ref.,⁴³ ^d from Ref⁴⁴

1). What is most important here is that the $3d - 3d$ interaction is so weak that the actual bond occurs at longer distances, in the $4s - 4s$ area. This may lead to serious errors on the geometry of the dimer, but especially in larger clusters in which the $4s$ interaction would always be the leading one and the clusters would show unusual large bond lengths among distinct Cr-Cr sites. To make things worse, the fundamental vibrational frequency of the Cr dimer is computed at 70 cm^{-1} , about 400 wavenumbers lower than the experiment. It is evident from what described above, that with the default choice for the IPEA shift we are unable to reproduce our PES and therefore a new value of this parameter must be sought for.

For $\epsilon = 0.10$ the potential surface reproduces the experimental flat region, corresponding to the $4s - 4s$ interaction, however in the region of the $3d$ minimum only a small shoulder is observed (see orange line in Figure 1). When the IPEA shift is increased to higher values, the shape of the $3d$ minimum is improved, while the behavior in the $4s$ region remains almost well-described. This means that the IPEA modifies mainly the $3d - 3d$ interaction while the $4s - 4s$ is properly accounted for and rather independent from this parameter. Finally, we find that the best agreement with the experiment is achieved at a value of about $\epsilon = 0.45$ (see purple line in Figure 1) where the shape of

the curve reproduces accurately the region around the first minimum, both the shape and the energy, as well as the small minimum at longer distances.

Regarding bond lengths, we find that they are decreased with increasing IPEA shift and the best agreement with the experiment corresponds to $\epsilon = 0.50$ (1.681 Å calculated and 1.679 Å experimental). The $g1$ Hamiltonian also leads to satisfactory values of R_e (1.682 and 1.662 Å). The dissociation energy increases with higher values of IPEA and the best result corresponds to $\epsilon = 0.45$ (1.50 eV calculated and 1.53 eV experimental). Finally, the best agreement with experiment for the $\Delta G_{1/2}$ is obtained with $\epsilon = 0.40$ (468 cm^{-1}) compared to the experimental 452 cm^{-1} .

Based on the above results, we decided to proceed with a IPEA shift parameter value of 0.45, which gives the best compromise in terms of PES facets, dissociation energy, equilibrium bond length and fundamental vibrational frequency.

3.2 Accuracy of quantum chemical calculations: RASPT2 vs CASPT2 results

The previous part of this work has been devoted to the analysis of the effects of the IPEA shift on some properties of the chromium dimer, using high level CASSCF/CASPT2 calculations. However, as it was mentioned earlier, the main goal of this paper is to benchmark the capabilities of the recently proposed RASPT2 method which has been previously successfully employed.^{21,23-25} In this part of the work we would like to check the performance of the RASPT2 method on some properties of the Cr_2 dimer and, in order to do so, we decided to probe in a consistent way the size of the RAS subspaces (RAS1, RAS2, RAS3) with respect to the CASPT2 results.

In Figure 2 we represent a qualitative molecular orbital diagram for the dimer. This diagram will guide us in the distribution of the molecular orbitals in the different RAS subspaces. The nomenclature used in these calculations is the following: $(n_e \text{ in } n_o)/(n_{e2} \text{ in } n_{o2})/n$, where n_e in n_o is the total number of electrons distributed in the total number of orbitals in the whole active space, n_{e2} in n_{o2} corresponds to the electrons and orbitals in the RAS2 space and, finally, n is the number of excitations allowed from RAS1 and into RAS3. The calculations performed are the following:

CAS(12/12) : The CAS contains all bonding and antibonding combinations arising from the interaction of the five $3d$ and the $4s$ atomic orbitals of the two Cr atoms at the equilibrium bond length. The following molecular orbitals are obtained (Figure 2) : $4s\sigma_g$, $3d\sigma_g$, $3d\pi_u$, $3d\delta_g$, $4s\sigma_u^*$, $3d\sigma_u^*$, $3d\pi_g^*$,

Figure 2: Schematic representation of the molecular orbital diagram for the chromium dimer. The energy ordering is arbitrary and only for didactical purposes.

$3d\delta_u^*$. This level of calculation is the most accurate and will be used as reference for the RASSCF and RASPT2. In Figure 3, we immediately notice that in the CASSCF potential the $3d - 3d$ bond is virtually absent and is represented by a very small shoulder at about 1.80 Å. At increased distances, the energy profile becomes more stabilizing, with a large shallow minimum at about 3 Å. The facets of the PES change drastically with the inclusion of the dynamic correlation energy, thanks to the formation of a deep well in the $3d - 3d$ bonding energy (Figure 4). This allows to obtain the correct form of the potential, which leads to a correct description of the spectroscopic parameters in the CASPT2 results.

CAS(10/10) : In this calculation, we remove from the active space the $4s\sigma_g$ bonding and $4s\sigma_u^*$ antibonding orbitals and we correlate them perturbatively in the CASPT2 step. This gives rise to an erratic PES for both the CASSCF and CASPT2, since the effect of the CSFs produced by exci-

Figure 3: Potential energy surfaces calculated at CASSCF and RASSCF levels of theory. Bond distances in Å and energies in kcal/mol. For simplicity, the asymptotic zero energy taken as reference is total energy of the Cr atoms at a distance of 10 Å and computed at the CASSCF(12/12) level of theory. All others binding energies are depicted with respect to this value.

tations from (into) $4s\sigma_g$ ($4s\sigma_u^*$) is treated only perturbatively, and therefore not accurately enough to describe the $4s - 4s$ bond breaking. As a result, large deviations are seen in the 2.5 Å region, where the $4s - 4s$ interaction is dominant. At short distances the CASPT2 curve behaves accurately. The spectroscopic parameters are affected dramatically (see Table 2) with the exception of the equilibrium bond length. The dissociation energy is more binding by 2 eV and the vibrational frequency is reduced by about 30 cm^{-1} .

RAS(12/12)/(10/10)//2 : In this first RASSCF/RASPT2 calculation the $4s$ bonding orbital ($4s\sigma_g$) is included in RAS1 and the corresponding antibonding ($4s\sigma_u^*$) in RAS3. Single and double excitations are allowed from $4s\sigma_g$ and into $4s\sigma_u^*$. This active space is actually equivalent to the CAS(12/12), since RAS2 produces up to tenfold excitations, that can combine with the singles and doubles from RAS1 and into RAS3, therefore reaching twelve fold excitations. This equivalence is obviously reflected in the number of CSFs used to build the wavefunction in each of the two methods, as seen in Table 2.

Figure 4: Potential energy surfaces calculated at different levels of theory, together with the experimental curve. Bond distances in Å and energies in kcal/mol. For simplicity, the asymptotic zero energy taken as reference here is total energy of the Cr atoms at a distance of 10 Å and computed at the CASPT2(12/12) level of theory. All others binding energies are depicted with respect to this value. For this reason, the binding energies expressed in the figure are not equal (with the exception of the full CASPT2) to the D_e given in the Tables throughout the text.

RAS(12/12)/(8/8)//2,4 : The composition of the different spaces is the following: RAS1($4s\sigma_g, 3d\sigma_g$), RAS3($4s\sigma_u^*, 3d\sigma_u^*$) and RAS2($3d\pi_u, 3d\delta_g, 3d\pi_g^*, 3d\delta_u^*$). Basically, we exclude the most bound 3d orbitals, i.e. the $3d\sigma_g$, and its antibonding counterpart from the RAS2 space. We calculated the effect of double and quadruple excitations from RAS1 and into RAS3. The latter one is equivalent to the full CASSCF/CASPT2 (12/12). With the double excitations, the number of CSFs is reduced of about half, from 57168 to 29244. The CASPT2 PES is well described up to 2.5 Å, after this point the curve moves upwards compared to the correct behavior and higher excitations are needed for a proper description of this long range interactions. The RASPT2 equilibrium bond length and vibrational frequency (1.682 Å and 515 cm^{-1} , respectively) are in good agreement with the CASPT2 values (1.687 Å and 516 cm^{-1}), nevertheless, the dissociation energy is largely overestimated (4.23 eV compared to 1.50 eV). We can conclude that this level of approximation is accurate enough to describe the geometry of the dimer and the vibrational frequency, but not the dissociation energy.

Figure 5: Potential energy surfaces calculated at RASPT2(12/12)(0/0)//2,4,6,8,10,12 levels of theory, together with the experimental curve. Bond distances in Å and energies in kcal/mol. For simplicity, the asymptotic zero energy taken as reference is total energy of the Cr atoms at a distance of 10 Å and computed at the CASPT2(12/12) level of theory. All others binding energies are depicted with respect to this value. For this reason, the binding energies expressed in the figure are not equal (with the exception of the full CASPT2) to the D_e given in the Tables throughout the text.

RAS(12/12)(4/4)//2,4,6,8 : In this calculation RAS1 includes $4s\sigma_g$, $3d\sigma_g$ and $3d\pi_u$ orbitals, RAS3 includes $4s\sigma_u^*$, $3d\sigma_u^*$ and $3d\pi_g^*$, and finally RAS2 contains the following orbitals: $3d\delta_g$ and $3d\delta_u^*$. Up to octuple excitations are allowed from RAS1 and into RAS3. As in the former cases, the highest order of excitations corresponds to the full CASSCF/CASPT2. For the rest, we notice some interesting things for the RASPT2 results: the number of excitations influences slightly the equilibrium bond lengths: 1.641 Å for doubles, 1.681 Å for quadruples and 1.687 Å for sextuples and the comparison with the experiment (1.679 Å) or the CASPT2 (1.687 Å) is satisfactory. Especially, in the calculation with doubles that has only 2298 CSFs, about 20 times less than those of the full CASPT2, the geometry is reasonably well reproduced. Unfortunately, the dissociation energy is affected at greater extent for almost all RAS spaces, showing important discrepancies with the experimental values (see Table 2). In Figure 4 is possible to see the trends

just described: in the region of the first minimum, all the RAS spaces compare well with the experimental curve, but at longer distances only the one including sextuple excitations shows an acceptable behavior.

Table 2: Spectroscopic constants and number of configuration state functions (CSF) for different levels of calculation using the IPEA shift value $\epsilon = 0.45$. Rows in italic denote calculations that reproduce the full CASPT2 results with the same number of CSFs. Experimental values are also included. Distances in Å, vibrational frequencies in cm^{-1} and energies in eV. The D_e is computed following the PES from the Cr_2 ground state to the separated fragments in their ground states at the given level of theory. The D'_e is computed with respect to the isolated fragments at the full CASPT2.

Calculation	CSF	R_e	D_e	D_0	D'_e	$\Delta G_{1/2}$
CASPT2(10/10)	4956	1.689	3.40	3.37	1.10	389
<i>CASPT2(12/12)</i>	57168	1.687	1.53	1.50	1.53	516
<i>RASPT2(12/12)/(10/10)//2</i>	<i>57168</i>	<i>1.687</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>1.50</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>516</i>
RASPT2(12/12)/(8/8)//2	29244	1.682	4.26	4.23	1.41	515
<i>RASPT2(12/12)/(8/8)//4</i>	<i>57168</i>	<i>1.687</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>1.50</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>516</i>
RASPT2(12/12)/(4/4)//2	2298	1.641	4.17	4.15	0.30	208
RASPT2(12/12)/(4/4)//4	29164	1.681	5.94	5.90	1.35	502
RASPT2(12/12)/(4/4)//6	55126	1.687	2.33	2.30	1.53	504
<i>RASPT2(12/12)/(4/4)//8</i>	<i>57168</i>	<i>1.687</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>1.50</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>516</i>
RASPT2(12/12)/(0/0)//2 ¹	199	-	-	-	-	-
RASPT2(12/12)/(0/0)//4	7206	1.638	10.82	10.80	0.39	212
RASPT2(12/12)/(0/0)//6	37122	1.678	5.54	5.51	1.37	516
RASPT2(12/12)/(0/0)//8	55629	1.687	2.38	2.35	1.53	512
RASPT2(12/12)/(0/0)//10	57155	1.687	1.58	1.55	1.53	510
<i>RASPT2(12/12)/(0/0)//12</i>	<i>57168</i>	<i>1.687</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>1.50</i>	<i>1.53</i>	<i>516</i>
experiment	-	1.679	-	1.53	-	452

[1]In this RAS space most of the calculations have diverged and a complete description of the spectroscopic parameters is not possible.

RAS(12/12)(0/0)//2,4,6,8,10,12 : In this calculation, RAS1 includes the following orbitals: $4s\sigma_g$, $3d\sigma_g$, $3d\pi_u$ and $3d\delta_g$ and RAS3 includes $4s\sigma_u^*$, $3d\sigma_u^*$, $3d\pi_g^*$ and $3d\delta_u^*$ orbitals. RAS2 subspace is empty, which means that these calculations are similar to multireference CI, except for the fact that the coefficients of the molecular orbitals are also optimized variationally. Here we perform up to 12-ple excitations between RAS1 and into RAS3 subspaces,

with this latter one corresponding to a full CASPT2 (12/12). For sake of clarity, the results are represented in Figure 5. All the orders of excitations from RAS1 and into RAS3 produce reasonable results regarding equilibrium bond lengths (see Table 2), however the dissociation energies are quite poor at first, but improved notably with increasing degree of excitations. For example, with quadruple excitations D_e is 10.80 eV and with 10-ples is 1.55 eV very close to the CASPT2 value (1.50 eV). The vibrational frequencies are satisfactory from sextuple excitations and up. Obviously, the best RASPT2 space is the one that includes 10-ple excitations, however this level of calculation generates roughly the same number of configuration state functions (57155) as CASPT2 (57168) and there is no real computational advantage. A reasonable compromise is the RASPT2(12/12)(0/0)//6 space, with 37122 CSFs, and very good equilibrium bond length and vibrational frequency are obtained.

Vibrational Levels : As a further litmus test for the RASPT2 method, we decided to compare higher vibrational levels with the available experimental values, from $\nu=1$ to $\nu=9$, for $\Delta G_{v+1/2}$ and $G(v) - G(0)$.²⁶ In Table 3 we report a summary of all the results. The last row identifies the mean unsigned error, MUE. The first eye-catching feature is that the previous results by Roos carry an overall error lower than the present calculations, including our full CASPT2. This is probably due to the fact that to describe with even more accuracy the upper vibrational levels, we would need to include the 4p orbitals in the active space. Moreover, apart from the RAS spaces with the lowest number of excitations (in the table referred as A2, C//2 and D//4), we obtain a satisfactory agreement between the RASPT2 values and the experiment, with MUE varying between 23 and 45 cm^{-1} for $\Delta G_{v+1/2}$ and between 34 and 77 cm^{-1} for $G(v) - G(0)$. It is noteworthy that cancellation of errors brings some of the RASPT2 active spaces to be more accurate than the full CASPT2.

3.3 Discussion and Conclusions

The RASPT2 method carries limited advantages over the CASPT2 in the specific case of the Cr dimer. The best compromise of accuracy vs computational advantage is obtained by the RASPT2(12/12)/(8/8)//2, which describes quite well the equilibrium bond length and the vibrational frequency. Unfortunately, the dissociation energy is somewhat off, as it is in most of the RAS spaces we have chosen. To fix this problem and to get more accurate values for the dissociation, we then decided to make use of a simple workaround. Instead of taking the atoms at large distance and compute the

Table 3: Calculated vibrational frequencies. Nomenclature: CAS and RAS stands for CASPT2 and RASPT2, respectively. A1 and A2 stand for active spaces of type (12/12) and (10/10). A0 results are taken from³¹. B for (12/12)/(8/8). C for (12/12)/(4/4) and D for (12/12)/(0/0). Experimental data are taken from Ref.²⁶ Mean unsigned error (MUE) are given in the last row.

ν	$\Delta G_{v+1/2}$											exp.
	CAS A0	CAS A1	CAS A2	RAS B//2	RAS C//2	RAS C//4	RAS C//6	RAS D//4	RAS D//6	RAS D//8	RAS D//10	
1	413	516	389	515	208	502	504	212	516	512	510	452
2	439	477	140	436	171	442	443	178	452	452	450	423
3	428	431	130	371	156	382	381	161	396	391	391	405
4	401	373	146	336	148	340	326	150	356	338	340	365
5	370	322	153	300	144	313	284	142	320	297	299	340
6	335	281	156	270	140	289	250	136	296	265	266	315
7	298	244	159	243	137	271	222	131	280	237	236	280
8	259	204	161	221	133	258	198	128	264	214	208	250
9	218	151	162	201	130	249	173	125	254	192	176	210
MUE	22	38	160	33	186	25	45	186	23	36	37	–
	$G(v) - G(0)$											
1	413	516	389	515	208	502	504	212	516	512	510	452
2	852	993	529	951	379	944	947	390	968	964	960	875±10
3	1279	1424	659	1322	535	1326	1328	551	1364	1355	1351	1280±10
4	1681	1797	805	1658	683	1666	1654	701	1720	1693	1691	1645±10
5	2050	2119	958	1958	827	1979	1938	843	2040	1990	1990	1985±15
6	2385	2400	1114	2228	967	2268	2188	979	2336	2255	2256	2300±15
7	2683	2644	1273	2471	1104	2539	2410	1110	2616	2492	2492	2580±20
8	2942	2848	1434	2692	1237	2797	2608	1238	2880	2700	2700	2830±20
9	3160	2999	1596	2893	1367	3046	2781	1363	3134	2876	2876	3040±20
MUE	65	93	914	76	1076	34	110	1067	65	75	77	–

energy with the same RAS space used at the equilibrium, we used the energy of the isolated atoms computed at the full CASPT2 level of theory. This energy is cheap to calculate because the atom has a reduced active space, i.e. (6/6), and a full CASPT2 accounts of only a small number of CSFs. If we take this CASPT2 energy as reference for the atomic fragments, the RASPT2 dissociation energies are improved. In Table 2, they are represented with the acronym D'_e . The maximum error is contained within about 1.2 eV, while

already with some higher order of excitations from RAS1 and into RAS3, this error can be contained within the 0.2-0.3 eV. It is evident that the improvement is huge, as the error is drastically reduced by factor of 3 to 5. This way of proceeding however introduced an imbalance between the active space used for the atomic fragments and for the dimer at the equilibrium. This imbalance holds at the CASSCF (or RASSCF) step, but it is virtually canceled out at the PT2 level, when also the $3s$ and $3p$ orbitals are perturbatively correlated using all virtual orbitals, restoring in this way a numerical size-consistency.

In conclusion, if one would like to study a cluster with more Cr atoms, it is wise to proceed with a balanced RASPT2 space, not necessarily too big, to obtain reasonable geometries and frequencies. For the dissociation energy, as explained above, it is always better to take the fragments computed with the most accurate method available, keeping the size consistency at the PT2 step.

We must also consider that in this paper we have chosen to benchmark an extremely complicated molecule that shows a heavy multiconfigurational character and a complicated potential energy surface. This had repercussions, as we have seen, not only on the RASPT2 method, but also on the IPEA shift, which we had to tune to a value of 0.45 for a correct description of the potential energy surface and the spectroscopic constants. It may be interesting to apply the RASPT2 method and check the default value of the IPEA shift for other transition metal dimers, where these limitations can be less pronounced and where RASPT2 may show significant computational advantages over CASPT2, contrary to what observed for the Cr dimer.

Overall, RASPT2 appears as a computationally viable alternative to CASPT2 for studying stationary points on a PES, but it may fail to reproduce some details of the surface, as shown by the peculiar case of Cr_2 .

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